

STRAIN RATE DEPENDENT MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE EQUINE HOOF WALL

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of fully hydrated equine hoof wall were examined at various loading rates in compact tension and tensile tests. Fracture toughness remained constant whereas all tensile parameters except ultimate strain were sensitive to strain rate. Equine hoof wall viscoelasticity does not appear to compromise ultimate tensile properties or fracture toughness at high strain rates.

INTRODUCTION

The equine hoof wall is a hierarchically organized structure formed from a protein-based fiber-reinforced composite. Resembling an obliquely truncated cone, it forms the outer load-bearing surface of the foot, suspending the bony skeleton via collagen fibers. The wall is subjected to high impact loading conditions and may experience large stress concentrations.

Hoof wall is composed of solid epidermal cells filled with a hardened polymer called keratin. Keratin is a bi-phase protein consisting of a fibrous α -helical phase and a globular matrix phase. Keratinized cells of the *stratum medium* (SM; middle region and bulk of the hoof wall) are strongly adhered to one another, and they combine to form one of two substructures depending on origin: 200-300 μm diameter tubules that run the length of the hoof, or an intertubular cellular matrix (Fig. 1). Bertram and Gosline [1],[2] found that the middle region of the SM in equine hoof wall is highly resistant to fracture; its composite design both at the macro and micro scales is believed to be a factor of paramount importance.

Most biological materials are neither purely elastic nor purely viscous in mechanical behaviour; instead, they show a combination of both and are hence termed viscoelastic. The hydration dependence on fracture toughness of hoof wall [2] is one manifestation of viscoelasticity. A consequence of viscoelasticity is mechanical strain rate-sensitivity and a possible transition from a ductile or pseudo-ductile to brittle behaviour. This effect is important to the horse since, as with most structural biomaterials, loading conditions are not always static. As gait pattern and speed change, so does hoof wall loading rate. Strain rates on the surface of equine hoof wall have been shown to vary between 0.02 and 1.7 strain s^{-1} for a horse travelling from 1 to 6 m s^{-1} [3].

Surprisingly, the mechanical behaviour of hoof tissue at various strain rates has not yet been evaluated, and although mechanical effects of hoof viscoelasticity with loading rate may have significant consequences to the animal, they are still unknown. This study attempts to quantify fracture and tensile parameters of hoof wall tissue encompassing the entire SM at full hydration, and to determine if mechanical properties are strain-rate sensitive.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The SM from the toe region of hoof wall samples was shaped into two types of test specimens: compact tension (CT) and tensile specimens. Samples were shaped to appropriate dimensions for CT tests following ASTM [4] guidelines as closely as possible, however, the morphology of the foot made some modifications unavoidable. Although specimen thickness was occasionally less than that recommended, the full thickness of the SM was used. To simulate an *in situ* fracture condition to which the hoof would regularly be exposed, CT pieces were notched parallel to the longitudinal axis of the tubules and across the wall thickness using a band saw (0.6 mm thick blade) and the notch front was sharpened with a single edge razor blade. The graphical method used to determine the fracture toughness parameter, J , was adapted from Landes and Begley [5] and required that a number of specimens be produced with varying initial notch lengths. After preliminary testing, it was decided that only specimens with notch length (a) to width (W) ratios below 0.65 be used to determine J , as the stress field at the notch front of specimens with a/W ratios greater than this were thought to be influenced by the end of the sample. Specimens were tested at full hydration at approx. 20°C.

Tensile specimen morphology was based on dimensions recommended by ASTM [6], however, since the length of hoof columns was limited by the size of the hoof, the overall length was often less than that recommended. Specimen thickness was greater than that recommended in order to include the entire thickness of the SM. Samples were milled to shape using an aluminum template and a reference bar was drawn on the inner hoof face of each sample with a black wax pencil to act as a strain reference during the experiment. Testing was performed at full hydration at approx. 20°C.

Figure 1. Clockwise from upper left: Front view of the equine hoof wall showing example positions from where samples were obtained; Sketch of a hoof wall sample showing cells forming tubules and intertubular matrix (bar = 100 µm; after Bertram and Gosline [1]); Tensile specimen ($L_0 \approx 25$ mm, $L_1 \approx 36$ mm, $L_2 \approx 66$ mm); CT specimen ($W \approx 24$ mm)

TEST PROTOCOL AND DATA ANALYSIS

Slower strain rate experiments employed an Instron testing machine (model 1122) with a 500kg load cell. The cross-head speed was limited to $1.67 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$; therefore a large (3.15 m total height) pendulum was constructed to determine mechanical properties at higher strain rates (impact). Four cross-head rates were used in each test type: 1.67×10^{-5} , 1.67×10^{-3} , 1.67×10^{-2} and $2.49 \pm 0.27 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (mean \pm 1SD) for CT tests, 8.33×10^{-5} , 1.67×10^{-3} , 1.67×10^{-2} and $3.89 \pm 0.40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (mean \pm 1SD) for tensile tests (corresponding to tensile strain rates, $\dot{\epsilon}$, of $1.58 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.20 \times 10^{-3}$, $3.17 \times 10^{-2} \pm 0.48 \times 10^{-2}$, 0.334 ± 0.037 , and $70.0 \pm 4.6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (mean \pm 1 SD), respectively). Our test range was believed to encompass the range of strain rates to which an animal is likely to subject the hoof, including local strain rates experienced at the ground contact surface and at a crack front during high speed locomotion.

Instron fracture tests were conducted in mode I crack mouth opening in distilled water (DW). The upper clevis used in the Instron tests was designed to allow the cross-head to reach speed before loading the specimen in faster experiments. Experiment duration for CT tests were approx. 1900, 15, 1.5 and $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}$ (sample intervals were 1, 0.04, 0.008 and $3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$, respectively) for the 1.67×10^{-5} , 1.67×10^{-3} , 1.67×10^{-2} and 2.49 m s^{-1} tests, respectively. Data from the Instron were fed directly to a PC, where load (kg) and time (s) data were converted to force (N) and displacement (m), respectively. An initial low stiffness (toe) region of the curve was the result of inherent system compliance and was excluded from data analysis by fitting a linear regression through the linear portion of the curve, extrapolating to the zero load level and using the regression line over the initial nonlinear range.

Experimental design for fracture tests at impact loading was similar in principle to that for slower test rates, with the weighted, swinging end of a pendulum providing the energy to move the "cross-head" at high velocities. A specimen was mounted in clevis grips horizontal to the floor; the front and back clevises were attached to a custom-built force transducer and an impact T-bar, respectively. Specimens were regularly sprayed with DW. Displacement was measured with two devices simultaneously: 1) An optical displacement transducer (ODT; Optek Technology Inc. model OPB700; Carrollton, Texas) attached directly to a clevis and 2) a goniometer positioned at the pendulum pivot to provide an indirect measurement of displacement. Displacements recorded from the ODT were used in the first (approx. 1/4) part of the experiment; goniometer recordings were used for the remaining part when optical measurements became unreliable. The arm of the pendulum was pulled back such that the weighted end was raised approx. 0.6 m. Force and displacement data were collected with a Data Precision digital oscilloscope (model Data 1000A) and were transferred to a PC for analysis.

Force-displacement records for each set of experiments were integrated to obtain a series of energy curves for each notch length. Since specimen thickness varied slightly between samples, energy values were scaled for a 10 mm thick sample. By finding the energy value at a particular displacement for each crack length, a series of energy curves was generated and a linear equation was fit (Tablecurve 2-D, Jandel Corp.). The J-integral was determined by finding the negative value of the slope of this line for a critical displacement value and dividing by 10 mm. Rather than generate a number of these curves for each critical displacement, the coefficients of these curves were fit to a polynomial function (Tablecurve 2-D, Jandel Corp.) and an expression was obtained whose partial derivative was divided by 10 mm to provide the J-integral. The polynomial required that the critical displacement be known before the J value could be calculated. This was defined in our study as the point at which any further notch opening resulted in crack propagation. CT specimens fractured at a cross-head rate of $1.67 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ were visually inspected during testing to determine an average failure load. The load at failure was determined by referring to the corresponding load traces and calculating the failure load percentage of maximum load. The maximum load was defined as the first peak in load prior to any fall in the load, regardless of any subsequent increase. This criterion for

determination of the critical displacement was used for all strain rates.

Tensile test displacement values were obtained directly from the specimen by filming the marked reference bar with a Panasonic video camera (model WV-BL200) which interfaced with an IPM video dimension analyzer (VDA; model 303). Outputs of the Instron and VDA were transferred to a PC where load (kg) and displacement (m) values were converted to stress, σ (N m^{-2}) and strain, ϵ . Ultimate data were not used from specimens which failed at any area other than the parallel region of the test specimen.

Due to the short duration of impact tests, it was not possible to determine strain by filming a reference bar drawn on the specimen. Instead, strain had to be determined indirectly by measuring the movement of the T-bar (*i.e.* cross-head) with the ODT and goniometer. A pseudo-strain was calculated as cross-head movement divided by specimen length, L_1 (see Fig. 1). The pseudo-strain values were converted to an estimate of the actual strain by applying a correction factor that was obtained from Instron tests on identical tensile samples in which we measured both pseudo-strain and actual strain. The Instron-based correction factor was applicable to the impact apparatus because the machine compliances were very similar and because more than 99% of the total system compliance resulted from deformation of the specimen. System resonances were filtered out quite easily from impact data with minimal signal distortion using a fourth order zero phase shift Butterworth's digital filter [7] with a 1.0 kHz and 2.0 kHz cut-off frequency (for tensile and CT impact data, respectively) implemented in software.

A low pass filter within the Instron limited the frequency response of the system and consequently affected data from higher test rates (*i.e.* tests conducted at cross-head rates of 1.67×10^{-3} and $1.67 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) for both CT and tensile tests. A PC program was written to accept a time series and decompose the data into a power spectrum using a fast Fourier transform (FFT). Correction factors (magnitude and phase) obtained from the spectral analysis of the Instron load cell/electronics were applied to the power spectrum, and the time series was then reassembled using a reverse FFT. This procedure was sensitive to very small artifacts present in the original force curve and the reverse transform contained a small ripple from the higher harmonics. Therefore, the corrected data were smoothed with a fourth order digital Butterworth's filter [7]. A similar method was used in experiments at the highest Instron cross-head speed to correct a small phase delay generated by the VDA system. These procedures were verified by correcting a triangle waveform that had been filtered by a single pole, low pass, analog filter.

Figure 2. Typical stress-strain curves for each of the four strain rates used in this study

RESULTS

Sample tensile tests for each strain rate are shown in Fig. 2 and mechanical test results are summarized in Table 1. E_i , total energy, and maximum stress (σ_{max}) showed a significant increase with increasing strain rate. From strain rates of 1.58×10^{-3} to 70.0 s^{-1} , E_i changed from $0.282 \pm 0.065 \text{ GN m}^{-2}$ to $0.848 \pm 0.155 \text{ GN m}^{-2}$ (mean \pm 1SD), total energy rose from $5.36 \pm 1.07 \text{ MJ m}^{-3}$ to $9.71 \pm 0.48 \text{ MJ m}^{-3}$ (mean \pm 1SD) and σ_{max} increased from $17.4 \pm 2.5 \text{ MN m}^{-2}$ to $30.9 \pm 0.4 \text{ MN m}^{-2}$ (mean \pm 1SD). Although E_i rose with strain rate, curves were very similar after a region where the slopes of the stress-strain curves showed a rapid drop (see Fig. 2). A small increase in the mean maximum strain, ϵ_{max} , from 0.448 ± 0.047 to 0.510 ± 0.084 (mean \pm 1SD) was found with increasing strain rate, however, differences were not statistically significant.

The critical load for CT tests at $1.67 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ was $98.9 \pm 0.8\%$ (mean \pm 1SD) of the maximum load. J-integral values remained constant with test rate ($11.8 \pm 3.1 \text{ kJ m}^{-2}$ = mean \pm 1 SD; Fig. 3) and stable fracture was evident in all samples at all test rates.

Table 1. Summary data for tensile tests

Strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$ ($\epsilon \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Initial modulus, E_i (GN m^{-2})	Total energy (MJ m^{-3})	Maximum stress (MN m^{-2})	Maximum strain
1.58×10^{-3}	0.282 (4)	5.36 (3)	17.4 (3)	0.448 (3)
(0.20×10^{-3})	(0.065)	(1.07)	(2.5)	(0.047)
3.17×10^{-2}	0.316 (4)	5.57 (3)	18.8 (3)	0.431 (3)
(0.48×10^{-2})	(0.047)	(2.28)	(4.62)	(0.131)
0.334	0.473 (4)	8.47 (3)	25.4 (3)	0.498 (3)
(0.037)	(0.094)	(1.02)	(2.2)	(0.040)
70.0	0.848 (4)	9.71 (2)	30.9 (2)	0.510 (2)
(4.6)	(0.155)	(0.48)	(0.4)	(0.084)

Note: Numbers in parentheses adjacent to mean values are N, numbers below in parentheses are ± 1 SD.

Figure 3. Scatter plot of J-integral plotted against log cross-head rate for CT tests. J-integral was unaffected by strain rate (one-way ANOVA, $p > 0.05$). Each point represents one sample

DISCUSSION

Mechanical strain rate sensitivity is characteristic of viscoelastic materials and has been noted in many biological materials including wool, compact bone, cranial bone, antler and wood. The viscous components of wool are likely matrix proteins [8] intimately associated with water molecules; the fibrous phase appears to contribute initial elasticity. As with other hard α -keratins, a mechanical yield region of declining stiffness precedes a post-yield region characterised by a gradual rise. Based on mechanical data from wool, Feughelman [9] has recently postulated a simple model to explain the mechanical behaviour of α -keratins. He suggested that microfibrils (or the fibrous phase) are responsible for the initial (up to a few percent strain) linear or Hookean region. Further extension induces a yield resulting from an apparent molecular breakdown of the fibrous phase, whereby a portion of the α -helical fibers are transformed to β -sheet structures [10], and a concomitant movement of microfibrils closer to one another. Microfibrils eventually displace water molecules such that globular matrix proteins are squeezed by approaching microfibrils. Extension of matrix proteins is believed responsible for the increase in stiffness in the post-yield region.

Wool may be considered as a simple composite, the mechanical behaviour of which may be rationalized using rudimentary composite theory. Horn and hoof, however, are composed of numerous levels of structural hierarchy and should not be considered as simple composites. At the microscopic level, cells are filled with a unidirectional, molecular-composite of α -helical fibers embedded in a cross-linked protein matrix. These cells are disc-like in shape and are arranged in layers; the orientation of the molecular composite lies in the plane of these layers. At the next higher level, these layers can be arranged into one of two patterns: 1) hollow tubules formed from concentrically arranged lamellae or 2) intertubular matrix of stacked layers running at large angles relative to the long axis of tubules. Tubules appear to reinforce a relatively weak plane between layers of the intertubular matrix [1]. The tubule-intertubular matrix relationship is not quite analogous to a hollow-fiber reinforced composite, however, as the material composing both tubule and intertubular matrix are presumably similar with only intracellular fiber orientation differing between the two components. Further studies are necessary to determine the mechanical properties of each component and its possible contribution to the hoof.

The effect of strain rate on E_i over the range tested is not nearly as great as the effect of dehydration. Bertram and Gosline [2] found a 36-fold increase in E_i for equine hoof wall tested from 100% RH to 0% RH; our study showed only a 3-fold increase over five orders of magnitude of strain rate. Whereas E_i is considerably affected by strain rate, the shapes of curves at all strain rates are generally similar in the post-yield region (see Fig. 2).

Increased material stiffness allows for a higher ultimate stress, as more bonds in the viscous component of the wall are loaded and consequently the system is capable of accepting a higher energy input. The maximum strain does not change, however, as the material fails when molecules are fully extended and covalent bonds are broken; thus the extension to maximum alignment is strain rate independent. Our results differ from those of Evans *et al.* [11] for equine cortical bone loaded in tension at various strain rates. Their results for bone showed, in general, a peak in mechanical properties at a strain rate around 0.1 sec^{-1} , a rate likely to be experienced by a galloping horse. The decline in properties beyond this rate was attributed to a gradual transition from pseudo-ductile to brittle behaviour. The functional significance of our findings are clear: as a horse accelerates, increased skeletal loading is matched with a concomitant rise in tensile properties, allowing the hoof to absorb more energy at impact. It is likely that the equine hoof wall evolved to exploit the natural mechanical behaviour of viscoelastic solids, the abundance of lipids in the *stratum externum* (outer-most layer of the hoof wall) reflecting a need to maintain a certain level of hydration.

Our J-integral results suggest that there is no effect of strain rate on the energy released during crack propagation. Impact values of J are likely resistant to errors resulting from over smoothing, as J-integral values were obtained from *relative* changes in energy. There are, however, limitations with the use of J. The method in which J was determined assumes self-similarity. In our specimens, stable fracture proceeded at an angle to the tubule axis in the middle SM. Fortunately, this pattern was generally observed in specimens at all test rates such that although absolute values of toughness may not be as precise as desired, relative values are still valid.

Another required condition which was unavoidably violated with the use of this material was isotropy. Preliminary examination of the fracture surfaces reveals a "recognition" of the tubular and intertubular components of the hoof wall by the propagating crack and that at the micro scale, crack progression may be sensitive to strain rate. Smoother surfaces of impact test specimens implies a less pseudo-ductile and a more brittle behaviour during crack propagation. Although informative, this behaviour also breaches the condition of self-similarity. On the micro scale, path short-cutting should reduce the energy input during fracture as less surface area is created. This reduction in energy was not, however, statistically evident in our tests. It is possible that the J-integral technique may not be sensitive to energy changes at this level due to the violation of the self-similarity condition at this scale. A degree of comfort can be found with the notch length insensitivity of J over the a/W range used (t-test; $p > 0.05$ for all tests). Bertram and Gosline's [2] J value of 11.9 KJ m^{-2} for middle *stratum medium* hoof samples tested in a similar manner agrees well with our slower test, verifying the repeatability of these tests.

Rough calculations suggest that the minimum thickness for plane strain conditions in equine hoof wall ranges from about 10 mm to 11 mm for highest and slowest strain rates, respectively. This result is serendipitous and although merely an estimate, implies that the condition for plane strain has not been violated in this study. It should be noted here that the equine hoof wall and hooves from smaller animals may be designed such that plane stress conditions exist *in situ*. Plane strain conditions are required for testing merely because toughness values will represent minimum, conservative estimate of toughness for a particular material. It would therefore benefit an animal to utilize a structure which is thin enough that plane stress conditions exist, yet thick enough to withstand large loads.

The authors would like to thank Dr. A. Poursartip for advice and encouragement in the application of fracture mechanics to the study of biological composites and Mr. W. McGill for developing the frequency response correction program.

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PHYSICAL PROPERTIES: THERMAL AND ELECTRICAL BEHAVIOUR
